

NEOLOGISMS IN MODERN ENGLISH AND THEIR TRENDS IN WORD FORMATION (BASED ON TEXTS IN THE MEDIA)

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Abstract. This article will talk about the role of neologisms in ensuring freedom of speech in our country, its introduction into science through oral speech when it is found that there is a lack of a term in one concept or there is a lack of details in the existing vocabulary.

Keywords: neologisms in modern english, their trend in word formation, in texts in the media.

НЕОЛОГИЗМЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ И ИХ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ В СЛОВООБРАЗОВАНИИ (НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ ТЕКСТОВ В СМИ)

Аннотация. В данной статье пойдет речь о роли неологизмов в обеспечении свободы слова в нашей стране, их внедрении в науку через устную речь, когда обнаруживается, что в одном понятии отсутствует термин или не хватает деталей в существующей лексике.

Ключевые слова: неологизмы в современном английском языке, их тенденция в словообразовании, в текстах СМИ.

A distinctive feature of neologism is its absolute novelty for most native speakers. The word is a neologism for a very short time. As soon as it begins to be actively used, it loses the sign of novelty and becomes commonly used. The emergence of a new word is the result of a struggle between two trends: the trends of language development and the trends of its preservation. This is due to the fact that “there is a rather strong tendency in the language to remain in a state of communicative fitness” [12,9]. A person who creates a new word (originator) strives for individualization and originality. Then the word goes through several stages of socialization (acceptance in society) and lexicalization (consolidation in the language system). Modern English has many ways of forming new words, the most productive among which are: affixation (prefixal and suffixal methods), word composition, conversion, reduction, reverse derivation, lexico-semantic method, phonological method (alternation of sounds and stress transfer in a word), as well as borrowings from other languages. However, not all of these methods are used to the same extent, and the specific weight of each of them in the word-formation process is not the same. With the help of word production and word composition, the largest number of new words are created. Within the framework of word production, two main ways of forming neologisms are distinguished – suffixation and prefix. A characteristic feature of English suffix neologisms is their functioning as scientific terms. For example, the suffix -on (elementary unit or particle) is used to create terms such as gluon ‘a new elementary particle in physics that glues quarks’, luxon ‘an elementary particle with zero mass’ [28,113-114]. The presence of a sufficiently large number of prefix neologisms demonstrates the increased role of prefixes in the word-formation process. The main sources of prefixes, such as acro-, bio-, xeno-, micro-, euro-, tele-, etc., are Latin, French and Greek. Their use, as a rule, is limited to the scientific and technical sphere. Many new words that have become widespread in the English language in the last 15-20 years are formed by word composition, consisting in the

morphological connection of two or more roots (bases). As a result of the word composition, a complex word or composite (Latin *compositum*) is formed. The considered neologisms are complex words formed mainly by simple addition of the basics, for example: *airmiss* “stewardess”, *ballpark* “stadium”, *think-tank* “collective brain”. Characteristic exclusively for the formation of English neologisms is such a way of word formation as conversion, which, in turn, is expressed through substantiation (transition to a noun), e.g.: *acrylic* “acrylic” → and verbalization (transition to a verb), e.g.: *woman* “woman” → *two man* (for example, a man) with the features of a woman”. Another way of forming neologisms in English is reverse derivation, which is the process of forming words by cutting off the word-forming affix, for example: *televise* “show on television” ← *television* “television” (in this case, the verb is formed by truncating the suffix in the correlative noun). A separate place in the formation of neologisms, in particular neologisms of the English language, is occupied by the lexica-semantic method, which arises as a result of the development of the semantic structure of the word, namely, due to the expansion or narrowing of already existing meanings, as well as metaphorical or metonymic transfers, for example: *feature* “an attractive opportunity provided by a computer program” ← *feature* “function; possibility” (narrowing of a more general initial value); *hardware* “hardware” (metonymic transfer, the basis for which is the material, namely, the metal that computer parts are made of (the hardware lexeme is also used to denote metal products). Initially, the term “telescope”, which occupies a special place in the composition of compressive word formation, is mentioned in connection with the method of forming new lexical units by superimposing morphs or morphs of one initial component on the morph or morphs of another initial component, since such an overlay resembles “the insertion of telescope tubes into each other” [42,406]. In modern linguistics, the concept of “telescope” has a broader meaning and assumes such a way of word formation, in which a new word arises from the fusion of the complete basis of one source word with the truncated basis of another source word or from the fusion of two truncated bases of source words. The value of the new token thus includes fully or partially the values of the structural components included in it [40,502]. In the scientific literature, this method of word formation is also known by the names “fusion”, “contraction”, “contamination”, “insertion word formation”, “hybridization” etc. Neologisms formed by this method are called “telescopes”, “telescope words”, “telescope names”, “bullion words”, “words-convolutions”, “words-hybrids”. In English, there are even more synonymous names denoting neologism-truncation, namely, blend-word, amalgam word or form, fusion word, composite word, overlapping word, conflation, coalesced word/form, telescope/telescoped word, hybrid/analogical neologism, brunch word, counter-word, cross-form, word blending, contamination, as well as humorous suitcase word, portmanteau word [39,128]. The variety of terms and the lack of an unambiguous interpretation of this linguistic concept can be explained both by the versatility of the phenomenon under study and the possibility of different approaches to its study arising in this connection, and, probably, by the relatively late emergence of this word-formation method. According to a number of scientists, the bulk of telescope words appeared only in the XX century, and with each decade this method of word formation becomes more and more productive. Back in the middle of the XX century, most linguists did not recognize telescoping as a separate way of word formation, pointed out its borderline nature relative to other ways of forming new lexical units. It was believed that telescoping only to one degree or another tends to one of the already traditionally existing ways of word formation,

namely, word composition, abbreviation, prefix. A characteristic feature of the structure of the telescope word is that at least one of its components is represented not by a whole, but by a truncated base, its fragment. This is what distinguishes this method of word formation from word composition [24,125]. The attribution of telescope words to abbreviations is also controversial, since most telescopes, unlike abbreviations, do not have a correspondence in free phrases, but are formed due to the establishment of associative links between two syntactically separate words [27,93]. As a means of communication, any language, being in close connection with the history and culture of the people, is constantly undergoing changes. Such changes are natural and, above all, reflected in the lexical composition of the language. Such processes as globalization, digitalization, informatization have given a huge impetus to the emergence of new words. The presence of a large number of neologisms demonstrates the flexibility and adaptability inherent in the English language. Currently, English remains the language of international communication, which determines its intensive development. Vocabulary reacts most sensitively to all changes in various spheres of society. Thus, the rapid formation of the global information environment, the intensification of human activity, various political, economic and social movements determine the process of replenishing the vocabulary and enriching the modern language with the formation of neologisms. Language is closely connected with culture and is the guardian of culture and its national identity. Vocabulary allows you to reveal the linguistic picture of the world of society, reflecting the historical and cultural processes taking place and allowing you to adequately perceive and use words that arise in real time. Language development proceeds in the process of its continuous improvement and enrichment at the lexical level. With the help of vocabulary, a person represents the current reality. One of the examples of the development of any language is the process of the emergence of neologisms, as prerequisites arise in society for naming new realities. In addition, the nomination of new realities and objects often reflects the national and cultural specifics of the life of the speaking collective. The appearance of neologisms is proof of the evolution of language. It should be noted that not every new word is fixed in the language. At first, this word is an occasional, then it is gradually assimilated by the language, becomes a neologism, which then either becomes fixed in the lexical system, or disappears. Researchers give various definitions of the concept of "neologism". Thus, I.V. Arnold calls neologisms words or phraseological turns included in the language with the development or changes in social relations, changes in everyday life and living conditions of people, which are felt by speakers as new. V.S. Vinogradov defines neologisms as "new words or meanings fixed in the language, which are called new objects of thought" [3,121]. N.Z. Kotelova notes that the specificity of neologism requires parameters-specifiers, namely:

1. the parameter "time": neologisms – new words of any period in relation to any of the previous periods;
2. the parameter "language space" (spheres and genres of use):
 - a) in languages in general;
 - b) in a given national language;
 - c) in a literary language;
 - d) in a given sublanguage;
3. the "novelty" parameter is associated with the definition of the type of neologism: a new meaning (semantic neologism), a new form (neologism is a synonym for an already existing word), both (actually a neologism).

According to the method of formation, neologisms are divided into semantic, lexical and lexico-grammatical. The semantic way is a way of changing the meaning of an old word. Lexical neologisms are neologisms that have arisen from other borrowing languages. Lexico-grammatical neologisms are new words that have arisen on an existing basis by affixation, transformation, word combinations, abbreviations. Proceeding from the fact that a neologism is a newly formed or borrowed word (phrase), or a derivative word created for new realities from a previously known one, we note that of the many different ways of word formation (affixing, word composition, merging, shortening, etc.), word composition and mixing of words are the most productive ways of forming new words. Different layers of vocabulary are developing unevenly, so the largest number of new words appear in the sphere of public and everyday life, recorded in newspapers and magazines, Internet publications, social networks, etc. Many trends can be traced in the neologisms of the modern English language: fashion, food, leisure activities, political views. Such neologisms reflect various processes of human activity in society and perform the function of codification of new experience. These processes include environmental issues, socio-political realities, and everyday lifestyle, which demonstrate changes in human behavior and in his relationships. Such processes lead to a change in people's thinking, their consumer behavior and is reflected in new words formed in various ways:

shame for running away – a sense of guilt for air travel, prompting people to choose another mode of transport, word composition;

emergency climate – an emergency climate situation. A situation in which urgent measures are required to reduce or contain climate change and prevent irreversible damage to the environment, phraseology;

plogging – jogging, which is carried out along the way collecting garbage, merging (lifting + jogging)

One of the unsolved problems of neology is the problem of the term "neologism". Neologisms differ from traditional canonical words by special connections with time, which are fixed by the collective consciousness. Lexicologists and lexicographers consider units to be new words that appear in the language later than some time limit assumed for the original one.

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